

INFLUENCE OF SPORTS EXERCISE ON WOMEN'S HEALTH

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Annotation. The article analyzes data from modern scientific literature and scientific research on one of the current issues in sports medicine. The influence of sports loads on the health of women has been studied by many researchers in the field of medical and biological foundations of sports training for women, and the problems of the physiological foundations of sports training methods among female athletes have been studied.

Key words: female athletes, health status, loads, reproductive function, sports training.

Introduction. After the publication of the Resolution of the Olympic Committee in 1972, equalizing the rights of both sexes to participate in sports competitions at any level, the rapid development of women's sports began [2, 3, 4]. The professional level of female athletes is growing from year to year; women are mastering more and more extreme sports [1, 6]. The rapid growth of sports results began to outstrip even the most daring forecasts [5, 7, 8]. At the same time, obvious successes in sports have not reduced intense passions about the existing contradiction: how to protect a woman from heavy physical activity, how to protect her from stressful situations that abound in elite sports?

The level of women's records is continuously increasing, training and competitive loads have reached such values that their influence on the body of athletes is on the verge of the maximum possibilities of individual adaptation [9, 10, 11]. This is confirmed by the already established trends in the participation of

women in competitions of the highest rank, and their setting high records even in non-traditional sports. No one is surprised by the two-day marathon races of female athletes or women's sports matches on wrestling mats and boxing rings. An increase in the number of heavy loads increases the elements of risk, increases the number of injuries, overexertion, overtraining and is often accompanied by the forced withdrawal of female athletes from sports [12, 13]. In 1993, the American Board of Sports Medicine described an association between three distinct but related conditions-eating disorders, menstrual irregularity, and osteoporosis.

The desire of women for high athletic results in many sports causes mixed assessments among scientists. There are many examples of women athletes successfully building their sports careers and their future fates being successful. Along with this, points of view are expressed about the negative impact of sport on the female body, figure, psyche, behavior, reproductive function, family relationships and personal life [14, 17, 18]. This cannot be ignored, and it is with regret that we have to admit that scientific research into the needs of sports practice is lagging behind. Theoretical developments do not keep pace with the expansion of the boundaries of women's sports, the training methodology in which should have its own distinct features. As some scientists emphasize, unfortunately, often medical control of health and, in particular, one of its most important indicators - the reproductive health of highly qualified athletes - is practically not carried out or is of a formal nature. And basically the physical well-being of an athlete is taken into account by her sports results or anthropometric data. Noteworthy is the fact that in modern literature, mainly foreign, great attention is paid to this area of sports medicine [15, 16].

Since the entry of women's sports into a phase of rapid development, reports began to appear in the medical literature about a higher incidence of menstrual and reproductive dysfunction in female athletes compared to the same indicators in the general population [19]. Thus, today, in some sports (for example, artistic gymnastics, ballet), the incidence of reproductive dysfunction often exceeds 72%.

In the process of searching for the causes and mechanisms of development of this phenomenon, two extreme points of view were formed. According to the first of them, reproductive function disorders in female athletes are not fundamentally different from those in the general population, and their high frequency is explained by the artificial concentration in sports of women with a high content of androgens in the body and a tendency to retardation. According to some reports, these qualities give such athletes an advantage over their peers in achieving high athletic results. On the other hand, the reproductive function of an athlete undergoes certain changes in response to the influence of constant physical activity, but these changes, according to supporters of this hypothesis, are adaptive in nature and, in essence, reflect the body's normal reaction to the influence of this factor. Issues of the influence of sports on the somatic and reproductive health of young athletes are reflected in a number of scientific studies [20].

In modern women's sports, there is a contradiction between the very convincing arguments of doctors about the dangers of sports activities for the health of athletes and the social situation when the majority of female athletes evaluate sports activity as an important element of their lifestyle, necessary for self-realization. Nature has endowed women with complex physiological processes that have no analogues in men: menstrual function and childbirth. The most important component of the "price" of adaptation of the athlete's body to the "tolerance" of large physical loads arising during sports training is a disruption of the rhythm of functioning of the female reproductive system [3]. However, as medical research has shown, menstrual irregularities in female athletes at the peak of their athletic form are part of a complex of adaptive transformations in the female body in response to stress factors (which include heavy physical activity). Menstrual irregularities in female athletes are a kind of "price" for the body's achievement of a high level of adaptation to intense training and competitive loads. Numerous studies have established that changes in hormonal status occurring during the menstrual cycle cause a complex restructuring of the neurohormonal regulation of the functions of

body systems, accompanied by changes in respiration, blood circulation, oxygen capacity of the blood, and the direction of metabolic adaptation, which naturally affects the performance of female athletes.

In modern sports, the training process for women is built, unfortunately, according to the generally accepted methodology for men, in which the dominant direction is to increase the volume of training loads. At the same time, heavy physical and emotional stress often causes overstrain of regulatory systems and depletion of the adaptive reserve of the female body. This leads to a reduction in the terms of performance of female athletes in elite sports and the “weeding out” of talented youth. Many female athletes leave sports without showing athletic results that are adequate to their functional capabilities. The specific characteristics of the female body are manifested in physical development, physique and physiology of individual body systems, in the degree of development of basic physical qualities: strength, speed and endurance.

If two decades ago the question of training highly qualified athletes came down mainly to planning the training process and implementing the plan without specific consideration of the menstrual cycle and the formation of menstrual function, now knowledge of the basic characteristics and properties of the body of a particular athlete is required, the patterns of the relationship between the volume of control and means and methods impact, essence and content of pedagogical management.

Modern elite sport requires research in the field of adaptive capabilities of female athletes, their physical activity as the main theoretical prerequisite for physical training. Scientific research in this area has been ongoing for a long time. They show that even hard physical labor is not capable of causing such adaptive changes in the human body that are observed in highly qualified athletes. This is explained by the fact that the intensity of training work is combined with extreme conditions of competitive activity. It is known that the main feature of adaptation in sports, unlike many other areas of human activity, is the multi-stage nature of

adaptation to extreme conditions. This is due to the fact that each successive stage of long-term sports improvement, each competition confronts the athlete with the need for another adaptation leap. All this cannot but place special demands on the phenogenetic characteristics of female athletes.

Conclusions. Thus, modern women's sports are characterized by the following trends:

- short-term sports career of female athletes;
- short sports experience: sports activities usually end before the age of 20;
- a sharp rejuvenation of women's sports. Most female athletes begin playing sports in childhood before the age of 10;
- the emancipation of sports, the development of non-traditional, new and purely "male" sports by female athletes is associated with the general trend of feminization of society;
- high opinion of female athletes about the positive impact of sports on their health, appearance, attractiveness and femininity;
- the value attitude of female athletes to sports activities, expressed in the awareness of its high importance in the formation of their character: sociability, determination, composure;
- in some cases, sport can develop negative character traits in female athletes - aggressiveness and cruelty.

A significant portion of female athletes begin to engage in sports to achieve high athletic results.

The main goals of female athletes are, as a rule, realized. Therefore, in the practice of modern sports, when planning a training load, the morpho-functional capabilities of the women's body should be taken into account. Redistribution of the volume and intensity of physical activity allows the coach to complete all planned training, while maintaining the health of the athlete - the expectant mother, increase the possibility of increasing her athletic performance and "extend her life in sports."

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